

AN EVALUATION OF THE $\pm 45^\circ$ TENSILE TEST FOR THE DETERMINATION
OF THE IN-PLANE SHEAR STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

S. Kellas, J. Morton
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, VA 24061.
U.S.A.

and

K. E Jackson,
NASA LaRC,
Hampton, VA 23665-5225.
U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

The applicability of the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test for the determination of the in-plane shear strength of advanced composite laminates is studied. The assumptions used for the development of the shear strength formulae were examined, and factors such as the specimen geometry and stacking sequence were assessed experimentally. It was found that the strength of symmetric and balanced $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates depends primarily upon the specimen thickness rather than the specimen width. These findings have important implications for the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test which is recommended by several organizations for the determination of the in-plane shear stress/strain response and the shear strength of continuous fiber reinforced composites. Modifications to the recommended practices for specimen selection and shear strength determination are suggested.

KEY WORDS: Test Method; Shear; Strength; Graphite/Epoxy; Specimen Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

An ideal shear test can be defined as one during which a known state of uniform and pure shear can be achieved. Even in the case of isotropic materials, this condition is difficult to attain and maintain for large deformations. For fiber reinforced composites the concept of a uniform stress state is relative and depends upon the scale of the constituent materials, the degree of anisotropy, and the laminate stacking sequence. In general, a state of uniform stress can exist only at the ply level and away from free edges. Consequently, errors are introduced in the shear stiffness determination when the strain is measured from a strain gage applied to a surface ply, and an average value of the shear stress is used. Inaccuracies in the shear strength occur when the ultimate shear load is divided by an average area when, in practice, failure occurs progressively after initiation at points of non-uniform stress.

There is a large number of test methods available for measuring the shear stiffness and strength of advanced composite materials. Each test method, however, represents a compromise between the

ability to produce a reliable and/or meaningful result, and the total cost or complexity of the test procedure. The $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test is the only test available which can provide reasonable expressions for both the in-plane shear stiffness and the shear strength. This test was first suggested by Petit [1] in 1969 and represents the modification of a technique, previously suggested by Tsai [2], for the determination of the shear modulus and strength from a 45° off-axis test. Petit [1] realized that a more representative shear stress/strain response could be achieved if a balanced symmetric laminate was used. The purpose of testing a laminate rather than a lamina was to eliminate the overall shear/extension coupling that existed in the off-axis specimen and provide reinforcement against the normal component of stress at $\pm 45^\circ$. Petit [1] showed that the $\pm 45^\circ$ test can yield a reliable shear stress/strain response for up to about 1.3% shear strain when compared to the cross beam shear test. At higher strains the test was thought to underestimate the shear stiffness and the ultimate stress due to the effect of the normal tensile stresses at $\pm 45^\circ$. On the specimen geometry Petit [1] suggested that, a suitable width has to be chosen so that the edge effect can be neglected.

Further contributions to the $\pm 45^\circ$ test were made by Rosen [3] who presented a simple technique which facilitated the direct determination of the stress/strain response. Using an equilibrium argument he showed that, provided that there exists a state of uniform stress, the average in-plane shear stress τ_{12} is given by;

$$\tau_{12} = P/2A (= \sigma_x/2) \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load, A is the average cross sectional area and σ_x is the average axial stress. From an elasticity solution, Rosen [3] expressed the ply shear strain γ_{12} , in terms of the axial and transverse strains ϵ_x and ϵ_y ;

$$\gamma_{12} = (1 + \nu_{xy})\epsilon_x = (\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y) \quad (2)$$

where ν_{xy} is in-plane Poisson's ratio of the laminate. From eqns.1 and 2 it follows that the in-plane shear stiffness G_{12} is given by;

$$G_{12} = \frac{\sigma_x}{2(\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y)} \quad (3)$$

From eqn.1, the in-plane shear strength, S_{12} , is given by;

$$S_{12} = P_{ult.}/2A (= \sigma_{ult.}/2) \quad (4)$$

where $P_{ult.}$ and $\sigma_{ult.}$ are the ultimate applied load and stress respectively. Clearly, eqns. 1 and 4 are based on average values for the in-plane shear stress, and the applied load, as well as the uniform stress assumption. Hahn [4], showed that eqns.1 and 4 are valid provided that there is no shear/extension coupling, ie; τ_{12} is purely a function of γ_{12} .

Problems associated with the stacking sequence were observed by Terry [5] who showed experimentally that the value of the shear strength S_{12} , from eqn.4, depends upon the stacking sequence. He reported that 16-ply laminates with stacking sequence $(\pm 45^\circ)_{4s}$ and $(+45^\circ_4/-45^\circ_4)_s$ exhibited different stress/strain responses within the final portion of the stress/strain curve. Most importantly, the average tensile strength of the laminates with blocked plies was 28.4% lower than that of the laminates with distributed plies. Terry [5] attributed this effect to the distribution of the edge stresses and concluded that the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test would produce acceptable results provided that the plies are stacked in as homogeneous an arrangement as possible. So far as the strength is concerned, results similar to those of Terry [5], were also reported by Kellas and Morton [6] from a strength scaling study. The tensile strength and the strain at failure of graphite/epoxy specimens with $(+45^\circ_4/-45^\circ_4/+45^\circ_4/-45^\circ_4)_s$ stacking sequence were found to be 36% and 60% respectively, lower than those of specimens, with $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_s$ stacking sequence. In the Kellas and Morton study [6], the width to thickness ratio, w/t, was kept constant which meant that, the effect of the edge stresses upon the strength of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates was similar. Therefore, the degradation in strength was associated primarily with the thickness of an individual ply within a laminate.

Following Rosen's [3] recommendations, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test was adopted by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) as a standard test method, D-3518, in 1976. The effectiveness of this simple test was recognized by many organizations such as the Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association (SACMA) and the Composites Research Advisory Group (CRAG). Consequently, the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test and the resulting data have gained wide popularity and acceptance in a variety of applications such as research and development, material selection and qualification, and structural design. Unfortunately, some of the assumptions involved in the test method for the determination of the shear strength, which were clearly stated by Petit [1] and Terry [5], are often overlooked. In particular, the effect of specimen geometry upon the strength of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates has not been given sufficient attention.

The objective of the present work is to investigate experimentally the importance of specimen geometry and the implications of the basic assumptions related to the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test, with emphasis on the determination of the in-plane shear strength from eqn.4. Some of the most important issues are:

- (a) What is the effect of edge stresses upon the strength of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates and how important is the specimen width?
- (b) How appropriate is eqn.4 to the determination of the shear strength?
- (c) What is the effect of in-plane stress non-uniformity?
- (d) What is the correct value for σ_{ult} in eqn.4?
- (e) What is the effect of stacking sequence upon the in-plane shear strength?

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

In order to study the effect of stacking sequence and specimen size, several $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates were moulded from AS4-3502 graphite/epoxy unidirectional pre-impregnated tape with the general lay-up; $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_n$ where $n = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 . The stacking sequences were denoted **A**, **B**, **C** and **D** for $n = 1, 2, 3$, and 4 respectively. Parallel sided specimens were cut from the moulded panels with general in-plane dimensions; $12.7 \times k$ mm wide and $127 \times k$ mm long where $k = 1, 2, 3$, and 4 . The specimen sizes were denoted **a**, **b**, **c**, and **d** for $k = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 respectively. The specimen size and stacking sequence combinations which were tested are shown in table 1. Note that two of the specimen size/stacking sequence combinations, **Ab** and **Bb**, conform to the ASTM standard D-3518, and **Ab** conforms to the SACMA SRM-7 recommendations for specimen configuration. The numbers of specimens which were tested are summarized in table 1.

Specimens were loaded on a servo-hydraulic testing machine, equipped with hydraulic grips, under constant displacement control. To ensure a uniform rate of strain for all specimen sizes, four cross head speeds were used; $0.04 \times k$ mm/sec, where $k=1, 2, 3$, and 4 , for specimen size **a**, **b**, **c**, and **d** respectively. All specimens were tested to complete failure, that is, until the specimens broke apart.

Experimental data were acquired in the form of applied load versus longitudinal extension using a PC based data acquisition system. The displacements were monitored with either a 25.4 mm gage-length commercial extensometer or one of four custom-built extensometers with scaled gage lengths of $38 \times k$ mm, where $k=1, 2, 3$, and 4 , for specimen size **a**, **b**, **c**, and **d** respectively. The gage length for the custom-built extensometers was defined by means of two parallel grooves. Each groove was scribed into a thin layer of soft epoxy (approximately 12 mm wide) which was brushed on the surface of each specimen, before testing. This technique was adopted following previous tests [6], which indicated that slipping of the extensometer knife edges could occur. Such slipping was evident only in laminates with off-axis surface plies and appeared to be compatible with fiber in-plane rotation following an accumulation of matrix transverse cracks throughout the specimen volume. The transverse strains were not measured since the study was specifically concerned with the in-plane shear strength of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates.

Correlation between the applied stress and damage propagation was accomplished through a combination of enhanced X-radiography and optical microscopy. Once the stress/strain response for a given specimen type was established, additional specimens were loaded to a predetermined fraction of their ultimate stress, unloaded and removed from the testing machine, soaked in zinc iodide solution and then X-rayed. Some specimens were also polished along their edges and optically examined under a microscope.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Data for each individual specimen were reduced and stored in the form of stress/strain plots. The average stress was obtained by dividing the applied load by the cross sectional area of each specimen. The strain was determined by dividing the measured displacements by the extensometer nominal gage length. The average value of the maximum attained stress and the related strain, for each individual group of specimens, are summarized in tables 2 and 3 respectively.

3.1 Stress/Strain Response Typical stress/strain plots are shown in figures 1 and 2. The difference in the stress/strain response of scaled specimens with equal width to thickness ratios, w/t , is shown in figure 1. Such specimens are; **Aa**, **Bb**, **Cc**, and **Dd**. Note that, the scaled specimens share the same stress/strain behavior up to an applied stress of about 150 MPa (or 1.2% axial strain). As the applied stress increases further, the four curves deviate in a systematic manner which depends upon the specimen size. Namely, the gradient of the curves decreases until it becomes zero and then negative. The stress at which the gradient of the stress/strain plots is first zero, will be referred to as the peak stress. Note that specimens **Aa** and **Bb** (8 and 16 plies respectively) failed soon after that peak stress was reached. On the other hand, specimens **Cc** and **Dd** (24 and 32 plies respectively), survived the first peak and reached a second peak through a process of apparent strain hardening. A comparison of the stress/strain behavior of specimens with different w/t ratios is shown in figure 2. Results for 8 and 24 ply laminates indicate that the stress strain response is independent of w/t . However, the response does depend upon the laminate thickness. Regardless of the w/t ratio, specimens with 24 plies or more exhibited two peaks in their stress/strain curves; for example see specimens **Ca** and **Cc** in figure 2.

3.2 Damage Development Close examination of the polished edges of 8 and 16 ply specimens revealed that damage initiates in the surface plies in the form of transverse matrix cracks which will be referred to as transply cracks. The applied stress at which these cracks initiate appeared to be independent of the specimen thickness and was equal to approximately 150 MPa. This corresponds to the stress level, up to which, scaled specimens share the same stress/strain response as shown in figure 1. At stresses greater than 150 MPa transply cracks developed in the mid-plane plies. The initiation stress for these cracks depended upon the laminate thickness and was slightly lower than the first peak stress. At or beyond the first peak stress multiple transply cracks initiated in all plies. The most important difference between the damage initiation in 8 and 16 ply laminates was in the distribution of damage, being more localized in the case of the thinner specimens.

It is thought that the apparent increase in stiffness, or strain hardening, following the first peak stress, results from the alignment of the fibers with the loading direction. This phenomenon will be referred to as fiber scissoring. For the determination of the shear strength, based on eqn.4, the stress/strain behavior beyond the first peak stress is irrelevant since extensive transply cracking has already taken place. Therefore, the average of the stress and strain values corresponding to the first peak, which are thought to be more relevant to the determination of the shear strength, were extracted from each individual plot, for specimens with 24 or 32 plies, and are presented in tables 4 and 5. It should be pointed out that, in general, the coefficient of variation for the measured stresses was much lower than that for strains, see tables 2-5. Moreover, for the same specimen types, the strains measured with the custom built extensometers were always slightly higher than those measured with the MTS extensometer, as indicated in table 3. This suggests that knife edge slipping which is associated with fiber scissoring can be eliminated using the groove technique for securing the extensometer knife edges.

4. DISCUSSION

The $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test is generally regarded as one of the most straight forward tests available for the determination of the in-plane shear stress/strain response of advanced composites. However, the assumptions and approximations which are associated with this test and, in particular, the determination of the shear strength are often overlooked. The stacking sequence and the laminate size are both very important parameters, however, the importance of these factors does not appear explicitly in the documents produced by the standards organizations. The ASTM recommendations on stacking sequence and specimen thickness selection, for example, are loosely defined. Namely, these are: balanced symmetric $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates with thickness determined by the fiber type, 0.5-2.5 mm for graphite reinforced plastics, that is, any even number of standard thickness plies between 4 and 20, stacked in any $\pm 45^\circ$ -type symmetric sequence. Even though, it is not a usual practice for blocked-ply laminates to be used in such a test, the exact stacking sequence or more stringent guidelines should be provided in the standards. SACMA specifies a particular stacking sequence; $(\pm 45^\circ \pm 45^\circ)_s$ (for the SRM-7 recommended test). Clearly this represents an improvement over other similar recommended tests which leave the choice of the stacking sequence to the user.

Two of the specimen size/stacking sequence combinations, **Ab** and **Bb**, which were studied herein, conform to the ASTM D3518, and **Ab** conforms to SACMA SRM-7 recommendations for specimen configuration. The shear strength, as calculated from the average σ_{ult} values in table 2, is underestimated by 4.5% if 8-ply specimens are used instead of 16-ply. An even greater difference occurs when the results from 8-ply specimens are compared to the results from 32-ply specimens. Focusing on the shear strength, we will attempt to isolate and discuss the reasons for such inconsistencies in the strength values and the dependency on specimen size, starting with the validity of the relationship between the ultimate axial stress and the in-plane shear strength.

4.1 The Validity of Eqn.4 The relationship expressed in eqn.4 was suggested by Rosen [3], who stated that the local shear stress, τ_{12} , in each layer is independent of material properties and equals to one half of the applied stress, σ_x . However, problems may arise due to the fact that the plane of maximum shear stress for the laminate is different than that of the individual plies, where failure will initiate. As shown in figure 3, the plane of maximum shear stress for the laminate is orientated at 45° , to the loading direction; but, for the individual plies, the plane of maximum shear lies at an angle $45 \pm \theta^\circ$. The difference occurs as a result of an in-plane shear stress, τ'_{xy} , which exists at the ply level only and is required for ply compatibility. Therefore, while Rosen's statement is correct, and holds for both the laminate and the ply level, the usefulness of eqn.4 depends upon the uniformity of σ_x , both across the width and through the thickness of the specimen. Clearly, if the average applied laminate stress σ_x is equal to the ply stress, σ'_x , then the average laminate shear stress, τ_{12} , will be equal to the ply shear stress, τ'_{12} . However, if $\sigma'_x > \sigma_x$ then $\tau'_{12} > \tau_{12}$ and hence the measured shear strength, S_{12} , will be underestimated. The ply stress σ'_x can be larger than the average laminate stress σ_x , due to the inhomogeneity of the composite laminate. For example, in every laminated composite, there exists a resin rich region between plies of different orientation. This region will have a much lower stiffness than the rest of the ply and hence it will carry less stress. Errors can also occur if the ply stress field is considerably altered by the presence of thermal residual stresses, which being self-equilibrating, will not affect the overall laminate stress field.

Small inaccuracies can also occur as a result of significant fiber scissoring which is a function of the shear strain. From eqn.2 it is apparent that, for a constant value of v_{xy} , the fiber rotation, in the plane of the plies, is proportional to the axial strain ϵ_x . For a Poisson's ratio $\nu_{xy} = 0.7$, for example, and an applied axial strain of 2% the fiber rotation is about 1° . Note that, the 2% axial strain corresponds approximately to the point where the first peak in axial stress occurs, see figure 1. Clearly there must be a strain limit beyond which eqn.4 cannot be applied due to large geometric changes. If the fibers are orientated at an angle other than 45° , then $\tau_{45^\circ} = \sigma_{ult}/2$ but $\tau_{12} \neq \sigma_{ult}/2$. However, there is an even more important factor that can render eqn.4 invalid, and that is the onset of damage. Once plies begin cracking, large local stresses will result and the local ply stresses can no longer be related to the applied stress in a simple manner. Moreover, the axial stiffness of the laminate will decrease at a rate which will depend upon the type of damage and the rate of damage accumulation. If all plies in the laminate

crack simultaneously and damage evolves uniformly in all plies then the result will be a steady reduction in axial laminate stiffness, which may also cause fiber scissoring. If, on the other hand, damage occurs in one group of plies first, the laminate stiffness will be reduced; but, in addition, the laminate will become unbalanced and will be subjected to shear extension coupling. In either case the relationship between the normal and shear strengths, given by eqn.4, will be invalid.

In summary, the validity of eqn.4, for a balanced and symmetric $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate, depends upon;

- (1) the uniformity of the ply stress, σ'_x , and its relationship to the laminate stress, σ_x ,
- (2) the fiber orientation, which for an elastic body is directly related to the shear strain, and
- (3) the state of damage within the laminate.

So far, in our discussion of the validity of eqn.4, we have assumed a state of plane stress which is, of course, only valid for relatively thin and wide laminates. However, for practical reasons, typical laboratory size specimens are relatively narrow, and the three dimensional edge stresses may affect their mechanical behavior.

4.2 The Edge Effect When the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test was proposed by Petit [1], he pointed out that, since there was no applied shear stress at the specimen edges, the ply stress τ_{xy} , must fall to zero at the free edge. He added that the non-uniformity of the in-plane shear stress can be neglected if a relatively large specimen width is used. Terry [5] attributed the differences in the stress/strain behavior between 16-ply laminates with stacking sequence $(+45^\circ_4/-45^\circ_4)_s$ and $(\pm 45^\circ)_{4s}$ to edge effects. In addition to the non-uniformity of the in-plane shear stress, τ_{xy} , across the specimen width, it has been shown by Murthy and Chamis [7], through a 3-dimensional finite element analysis, that σ_x is also non-uniform across the specimen width. At the free edges the value of σ_x was approximately 80% of the far field stress. They have also shown that the relative magnitudes of the interlaminar stresses, τ_{xz} and σ_z depend upon the w/t ratio. For $w/t = 4$, $\tau_{xz} = \sigma_z$, and for w/t greater than 4, τ_{xz} remains constant, while σ_z diminishes, until it is practically zero for specimens with $w/t=30$.

Clearly, we can conclude that there is a complex distribution of three dimensional stresses at the free edge, the magnitude and nature of which depend upon the w/t ratio, and the stacking sequence. The question is; how important is the effect of the 3-dimensional stress state at the edge of the specimen? If indeed, there exists a significant edge effect, this should be reflected in the stress/strain response of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates with different w/t ratios. The results in figure 2 show conclusively that there is no significant difference in the stress strain response of such laminates. The **Aa** and **Ab** specimens which have a w/t ratio of 12.5 and 25.0 respectively, exhibit a very similar stress/strain response. Likewise, **Ca** and **Cc** specimens which have a w/t ratio of 4.2 and 12.5 respectively, exhibit a very similar stress/strain response up to 8.7% strain. In fact, the premature failure in the **Ca** specimen was associated with high gripping constraints due to the very narrow specimen area held in the jaws. During these tests, 2 out of 5 specimens failed within the jaw area and the other 3 failed very close to the jaws. Moreover, it is shown in figure 1 that even though all four specimens, **Aa**, **Bb**, **Cc**, and **Dd** share the same w/t ratio (=12.5), each one exhibits a different stress/strain response depending upon the number of plies. Specimens having the largest number of plies exhibited the greatest strength and strain to failure.

4.3 The Ultimate Stress In addition to the validity of eqn.4, and the stress non-uniformity, it is important to define and determine correctly the value of the ultimate stress, in order to obtain a useful value of the shear strength. Ideally, σ_{ult} in eqn.4 should be the value of the applied axial stress at which in-plane shear failure occurs. A difficulty arises in that, failure initiates in the surface plies as a result of stresses normal to the fibers, and is followed by failure of the mid-plane plies. Thus, a $(\pm 45^\circ \pm 45^\circ)_{ns}$ laminate, for all values of n , contains four weak plies; two in either surface and a block of two plies in the mid-plane. The weakness in the surface plies results from the lack of transverse to the fibers support which neighboring plies supply to each other in any other location within the laminate. As a result, shear strain, γ_{xy} , develops at the surface and close to the free edges [8], which leads to large transverse to the fibers normal strains, ϵ'_2 , as indicated in figure 4. These normal strains can be large enough to cause failure. Therefore, a true shear strength as a material property cannot be

determined unless the effect of the premature ply failures on the surface and in the mid-plane plies of the laminate are eliminated.

While the failure of the surface plies can be attributed to the non uniformity of the strain near the edge, this type of edge effect is not a function of w/t . Therefore, a given group of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates, such as $(\pm 45^\circ)_n$ s, will suffer a similar free edge damage in their surface plies, irrespective of n and the w/t ratio. However, whether the damage is significant to the stress/strain response of the laminate, will depend upon n . The larger the total number of plies in a laminate the smaller the effect of the pair of damaged surface plies will be.

Strong evidence for the dependence of the ply strength upon the ply thickness was provided by Kellas and Morton [6] in an experimental study of scaled $(+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n/+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n)_s$ laminates with $n = 1-4$. They showed that, under the same applied stress transply cracks initiated in the thickest laminate first. In fact, for values of $n = 3$ and 4 , cracks were observed before external load was applied. Therefore, it is not surprising that premature failure occurs in the blocked plies of the $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_n$ s laminates which are located in the mid-plane of the laminates. Clearly, any type of symmetric and balanced $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate will be subjected to initial failure in the surface plies, followed by failure of the thickest block of identical plies, but the strength of a given laminate will depend very strongly upon the stacking sequence and, particularly, the manner in which the plies are blocked. This argument is supported by figure 5 which shows the dependency of the strength of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies upon the thickness of scaled laminates. Such dependency may be positive or negative depending upon the scaling technique used. The effect of the cracked pair of surface and mid-plane plies diminishes progressively as n , in the $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_n$ s, family of laminates increases. The exact opposite, of course, is true in the $(+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n/+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n)_s$ laminates which are scaled-up by increasing the ply thickness, rather than repeating the basic sublaminates $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_s$. Note that, in the case of $(+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n/+45^\circ_n/-45^\circ_n)_s$ laminates, the effect of the surface shear strain, which leads to the failure of the surface plies, will also be enhanced as n increases. The thicker a surface, $+45^\circ$, ply is the smaller the shear constraint from the neighboring -45° ply is and, therefore, a greater shear strain will develop on the surface.

The effect of premature failure of the blocked plies is also compatible with the 28.4% strength difference reported by Terry [5]. Clearly, the $(+45^\circ_4/-45^\circ_4)_s$ laminate is much more susceptible to premature failure both of the surface plies and the mid-plane plies when compared with the $(\pm 45^\circ)_4$ s laminates.

4.4 The Stress/Strain Response While all $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_n$ s laminates share the same initial stress/strain response, up to about 150 MPa, as shown in figures 1 and 2, there is a significant and systematic divergence at a higher stress, which is a function of the number of plies. This behavior can be explained in terms of the influence of the observed damage mechanisms. Until the surface plies crack, all laminates share the same stress/strain response. However, once damage initiates its effect is reflected in the stress/strain response and depends upon the total number of plies in a given laminate. The loss of the two surface plies followed immediately by the loss of the two mid-plane plies is obviously catastrophic for an 8-ply laminate, which, in effect, loses 50% of its load carrying capability. In this case, total failure occurs soon after the initiation of damage in the surface plies. However, in a thicker laminate, for example 32 plies, the loss of 2 plies out of a total of 32, is insignificant. Moreover, the failure of the mid-plane plies is also delayed considerably. Damage examination revealed that the mid-plane plies fail close to but prior to the point at which the gradient of the stress/strain curve is zero. Thus, for the 8-ply laminate the mid-plane plies fail at approximately 158 MPa as compared to 179 MPa for the 32-ply laminate. The 32-ply laminate is not only stronger than the 8-ply laminate but is also much more ductile in nature. The ductile nature of the 32-ply laminates is particularly evident beyond the first peak stress, where extensive fiber scissoring is accommodated by the damage tolerant single plies, where damage spreads evenly throughout the specimen volume.

4.5 Summary It has been shown that the strength of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates depends upon the stacking sequence and the laminate thickness. Moreover, it has been shown that irrespective of the laminate stacking sequence or thickness, initial damage will occur as a result of normal stresses in the corner of

the laminates, where the laminate free edges meet with the laminate surfaces. Consequently an applied stress value at which shear failure occurs cannot be determined for such a laminate. However, for a given choice of stacking sequence, such as $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_{ns}$, with a single pair of blocked plies, a reasonable value for the ultimate stress can be obtained if n is large enough, for example 4 or greater. In any case the in-plane shear strength, as determined from eqn.4, will always be underestimated. Note that, since premature failure occurs due to normal stresses in a mode I fashion, it is anticipated that for a given number of plies, the degree of underestimation will depend upon the material system. Systems, such as APC-2, with a high fracture toughness G_{IC} , will be less sensitive to premature failure and hence a more relevant value for the shear strength could be obtained.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effects of specimen size and stacking sequence on the determination of the in-plane shear strength, from the $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test, were studied experimentally. It was found that, for the (brittle) material system which was evaluated, the strength can be underestimated by as much as 14% depending on the thickness of the test specimen. This variation was observed between 8 and 32 ply specimens having a $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_{ns}$ stacking sequence, with $n=1$ and 4, respectively. The effect of specimen width and the importance of edge stresses on the stress/strain response and ultimate stress were found to be minimal, within the range of specimen width-to-thickness ratios from 4.2 - 25.0. Based on these findings, it is suggested that the requirements for the laminate stacking sequence for the in-plane shear strength determination, as given in the ASTM standards, be specified more precisely. These specifications should be chosen to minimize the influence of specimen thickness on the shear strength measurement.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] P.H. Petit, "A Simplified Method of Determining the In-plane Shear Stress/Strain Response of Unidirectional Composites", Composite Materials: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 460, 1969.
- [2] S.W. Tsai, "A test method for the determination of shear modulus and shear strength" Air Force TR AFML-TR-66-372, Air Force Materials Laboratory, 1967.
- [3] B.W. Rosen, "A Simple Procedure for Experimental Determination of the Longitudinal Shear Modulus of Unidirectional Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.6, October 1972.
- [4] H.T. Hahn, "A Note on Determination of the Shear Stress-Strain Response of Unidirectional Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol 7, July 1973.
- [5] G. Terry, "A Comparative Investigation of Some Methods of Unidirectional, In-plane Shear Characterization of Composite Materials", Composites, October 1979.
- [6] S. Kellas and J. Morton, "Strength Scaling in Fiber Composites", NASA Contractor Report 4335, November 1990.
- [7] P.L.N. Murthy and C.C. Chamis, "Free-Edge Delamination: Laminate Width and Loading Conditions Effects", Journal of Composites Technology & Research, JCTRER, Vol.11, No.1, Spring 1989.
- [8] R.B. Pipes and I.M. Daniel, "Moire' Analysis of the Interlaminar Shear Edge Effect in Laminated Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, April 1971.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This Study was supported by NASA Langley Research Center under grant NAS1-18471. Thanks are due to the contract monitor Huey D. Carden. The fruitful discussions with Robert M. Jones are also gratefully acknowledged.

Table 1: Specimen size and stacking sequence combinations.

Size (mm)	Number of Specimens Per Stacking Sequence			
	A-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _s	B-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{2s}	C-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{3s}	D-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{4s}
a (12.7x127)	16	5	5	N/A
b (25.4x254)	4	8	N/A	N/A
c (38.1x381)	N/A	N/A	8	N/A
d (50.8x508)	N/A	N/A	N/A	8

Table 2: Average ultimate stress.

Size (mm)	Average Ultimate Stress - MPa (Coefficient of Variation)			
	A-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _s	B-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{2s}	C-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{3s}	D-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{4s}
a (12.7x127)	159.34 (3.05)	167.54 (1.52)	197.40 (2.03)*	N/A
b (25.4x254)	159.27 (2.08)	166.78 (2.65)	N/A	N/A
c (38.1x381)	N/A	N/A	227.32 (3.78)	N/A
d (50.8x508)	N/A	N/A	N/A	248.62 (2.00)

* As a result of the low w/t = 4.2, exceptionally high stress concentrations due to gripping constraints obstructed true gage failures from occurring. Only three out of five replicate test results for ultimate stress and strain were deemed acceptable.

Table 3: Average strain corresponding to ultimate stress.

Size (mm)	Average Ultimate Strain - % (Coefficient of Variation)			
	A-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _s	B-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{2s}	C-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{3s}	D-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{4s}
a (12.7x127)	1.61 (6.14) 1.86 (5.97)*	N/A	9.30 (9.14)	N/A
b (25.4x254)	1.78 (4.49)	1.82 (5.86) 1.97 (6.08)**	N/A	N/A
c (38.1x381)	N/A	N/A	10.66 (4.67)	N/A
d (50.8x508)	N/A	N/A	N/A	10.83 (4.39)

* The displacement in 8 out of 16 specimens was monitored with a custom built extensometer with a gage length of 38 mm

** The displacement in 4 out of 8 specimens was monitored with a custom built extensometer with a gage length of 76 mm.

Table 4: Average applied stress at the first turning point.

Size (mm)	Average Peak Stress - MPa (Coefficient of Variation)			
	A-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _s	B-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{2s}	C-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{3s}	D-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{4s}
a (12.7x127)	N/A	N/A	165.33 (2.34)	N/A
b (25.4x254)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
c (38.1x381)	N/A	N/A	170.37 (2.67)	N/A
d (50.8x508)	N/A	N/A	N/A	182.09 (0.26)

Table 5: Average strain corresponding to the first turning point.

Size (mm)	Average Strain - % (Coefficient of Variation)			
	A-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _s	B-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{2s}	C-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{3s}	D-($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) _{4s}
a (12.7x127)	N/A	N/A	2.19 (12.26)	N/A
b (25.4x254)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
c (38.1x381)	N/A	N/A	2.37 (4.09)	N/A
d (50.8x508)	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.43 (4.28) 2.46 (3.90)**

** Values from custom built extensometer with a gage length of 152 mm, used in conjunction with the MTS extensometer.

Figure 1. Typical stress/strain plots for scaled ($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$)_{ns} laminates, where n = 1, 2, 3, and 4 for specimen sizes a, b, c and d respectively.

Figure 2. Typical stress/strain plots for 8 and 24 ply ($\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$)_ns laminates, where $n = 1$ and 3 respectively. The specimen in-plane dimensions are as indicated.

Figure 3. The relationship between the applied and local stresses at laminate and ply level. Plane and uniform stress conditions have been assumed.

Figure 4. The effect of the surface shear strain γ'_{xy} , at the free edges, after [8]. Note that, at the corners where the laminate surface meets with the laminate free edges, ϵ'_2 is much greater than the strain ϵ_2 anywhere else in the laminate.

Figure 5. The effect of stacking sequence and laminate thickness upon the shear strength of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates. Note that in the case of the $(\pm 45^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_n$ laminates with $n=3$ and 4 , the first peak stress has been used and **not** the maximum sustained stresses.